

Release kinetics of 5-aminosalicylic acid from halloysite

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Abstract

This paper investigates desorption of 5-aminosalicylic acid (5-ASA) adsorbed onto halloysite (HL). Desorption isotherms were fitted according to kinetic laws obtained considering release of 5-ASA from HL as the phase of desorption of the previously adsorbed drug molecules both inside the nanotubes of HL as onto the surface of clay particles and/or in the inter-particle spaces of their aggregates [28]. Desorption isotherms has been also fitted with other equations frequently used in drug release kinetics studies. The best fitting corresponded to the kinetic model proposed; in agreement with the results of adsorption [28].

1. Introduction

Modified drug delivery systems are ideally designed to improve therapeutic efficacy in comparison with conventional dosage forms. They are aimed to maintain therapeutic drug concentrations at the site of action, to minimise side effects and/or regulate release kinetics. Many drug carriers have been described for these purposes, being polymeric systems the most studied [1-6]. However, porous inorganic materials, including silicon derivatives, can show several advantages in drug delivery applications [7-9]. Combination between organic polymers and silicates are also attractive candidates for drug delivery, because they can display advantageous chemical and physical characteristics not exhibited by the individual constituents [10,11].

A number of reviews show that mathematical analysis of *in vitro* dissolution data can provide a scientific basis in the understanding of mechanisms of mass transport involved in drug release from modified drug delivery systems [12-20]. Nevertheless, it should be stressed that there is no universal mathematical model that can explain all the possible physical and chemical processes of drug release. A given model can indeed describe a given delivery system under well-defined conditions, beyond which it cannot be considered predictive. The predictive capacity and accuracy are key features for a model. Empirical models can be very flexible but they are not sufficient to predict the exact behaviour of drug release. When possible, mechanistic theories should be applied because they can explain release mechanisms. Many efforts were directed to the study of models aimed to describe the kinetics of drug release from polymeric matrices, especially in the case of heterogeneous systems. In 1961, Takeru Higuchi published what is likely to be regarded as the most famous mechanistic equation used to fit drug release [21]. The “Higuchi model”, initially valid only for systems with laminar geometry, was subsequently extended to other geometries and modified to consider different features, such as porosity [22-26]. Despite these improvements, it can be taken into account that most of the hypotheses postulated by this model are not reflected in real systems. The main advantage of the Higuchi equation, however, lies in its simplicity and it is often used for the analysis of dissolution data from a variety of dosage forms, providing approximate information about mechanisms that govern drug release. Widely used in the study of dissolution kinetics from controlled release polymeric matrices is also the so-called “power law” [27]. However, due to the complexity of the phenomena to be described, much more efforts are needed to devote to searching for real (mechanistic) models apt to adequately interpret the kinetics of dissolution from drug delivery systems. In particular, no models have been yet developed to describe drug release from porous inorganic solid sorbents.

With these premises, in this work a new mechanistic model was proposed, based on adsorption-desorption equilibrium between a model drug (5-amino salicylic acid) and an inorganic support (halloysite).

Halloysite is a naturally occurring aluminosilicate, chemically similar to kaolinite, having predominant hollow tubular morphology. Thanks to its special morphology, halloysite has been used as carrier for drug

encapsulation [28-31]. The *in vitro* release characteristics of different drugs from halloysite tubes have been described in the literature, showing sustained release properties in almost all cases [32,33]. It has been also demonstrated that coating the halloysite using cationic polymers can further enhance the retardation of drug release [34,35].

5-Amino salicylic acid (5-ASA) (also known as mesalazine) is an anti-inflammatory agent widely used in the therapy of ulcerative colitis and Crohn's disease. It can be administered orally, but it needs to be protected in order to limit the absorption in the upper gastrointestinal tract (stomach and small intestine) [36]. For this purpose, equilibrium, kinetics and thermodynamic aspects of adsorption of 5-ASA into halloysite tubes was investigated [28]. The drug was adsorbed by the inorganic support as a result of two subsequent processes: rapid adsorption (specific adsorption rates between 10.0 and 12.3 s⁻¹; $\Delta H = 7.59$ kJ/g) on the external clay mineral surface followed by slow adsorption (specific adsorption rates between 0.2 and 0.4 s⁻¹; $\Delta H = 42.28$ kJ/g) inside the halloysite tubes. The structure of the obtained loaded tubes was detailed by solid state characterisation techniques, including high resolution electron microscopy (HREM) coupled with analysis X-ray energy dispersive spectroscopy (X-EDS) and confirming the presence of the drug both at the surface and inside the halloysite tubes [31].

With these premises, in this work, *in vitro* release behaviour (mechanisms and kinetics) from 5-ASA halloysite adsorbate was examined on the basis of desorption kinetics. The satisfactoriness of the fitting was expressed by the correlation coefficient (R²). The results have been compared with other equations, widely used in literature for release kinetic studies (first order, Higuchi or "square root", Hixson and Crowell or "cube root", Peppas or "power law" and Weibull) widely described in the literature [21,27,37-40]. Comparison was done using adjusted correlation coefficients (R²_{adj}), where R² values were normalised as a function of the number of experimental points and parameters of each equation [14].

2. Experimentals

2.1. Materials

5-ASA analytical grade (Sigma Aldrich, Spain) was used as supplied. Halloysite (HL) from Zaragoza deposits (Spain) was kindly gifted by the Department of Inorganic Chemistry (Faculty of Sciences) of the University of Granada. It was milled (Ika[®]-Werke mill M20, GMBH & Co. KG, Germany) and sieved (125-250 μm) to eliminate coarse particles and aggregates. Porosity of HL showed a bimodal profile in the range 10-0.06 μm , the outer diameters of the individual tubes being about 0.1 μm and the specific surface area approximately 45 m²/g [31].

2.2. Sorption of 5-ASA onto HL

5 g of HL were dispersed under stirring (100 rpm) in 500 ml of 5-ASA aqueous solution (225 mg/l) at 40 \pm 0.1 °C for 24 h. This time was long enough to ensure that equilibrium was reached between the drug adsorbed and drug in solution [28]. The adsorbate (hereafter referred as 5-ASA-HL) were recovered by filtration and dried in oven at 60 °C. The amount of drug retained was determined by UV spectroscopy at 297 nm (Perkin Elmer[®], Lambda 25, Barcelona, Spain), resulting in approximately 4 mg/g dried HL.

2.3. Desorption studies

Desorption isotherms (weight/weight % of drug released vs time) were obtained on the base of "Dissolution Test procedures" for "Oral Solid Dosage Forms" [41]. Measurements were done on 2 g of adsorbate powder (<125 μm sieve fraction) using a AT7 automatic dissolution tester (Sotax, Spain) into 700 ml of dissolution medium (maintained at 37 °C), rotating at 50 rpm by means of the USP apparatus II. Three different media (purified water, 0.1 M HCl and pH 6.8 buffer (0.1 M HCl:0.2 M Na₃PO₄ 3:1 v/v)) were considered in order to evaluate the influence of pH and ionic strength on the release behaviour of the drug. Desorption was also studied following the USP method A for drug release of enteric-coated dosage forms. In this case, 525 ml

of 0.1 M HCl were initially placed in the vessels (acid stage); after 2 h, 125 ml of 0.2 M tribasic sodium phosphate were added to the acidic solution giving a final pH of 6.8 (buffer stage) and a total volume of 700 ml. At fixed times, 2 ml of dissolution media were automatically withdrawn (piston pump CY 7-50, Sotax, Spain) and collected in test tubes prior to be analysed (fraction collector C613, Sotax, Spain) by HPLC. Total amounts of drug released (Q_t) were calculated as follows:

$$Q_t = V_m C_t + \sum_{i=0}^{t-1} V_a C_i \quad (1)$$

where V_m and C_t are volume and concentration of the drug at time t , V_a is the volume of the sample withdrawn and C_i is drug concentration at time i ($i < t$).

2.3.1. Drug assay

The amount of drug dissolved was assayed by HPLC (series 200B/250, Perkin Elmer, Spain) according to [42]. The stationary phase was a Kromasil® C18 column (5 μ m, 250 mm \times 4.6 mm) (Teknokroma, Spain) and the mobile phase was a mixture of H₂O/CH₃CN (78/22, v/v) and acetic acid 0.5% (v/v). The flow rate was set at 1 ml/min, the injection volume was 20 μ l, the detector wavelength 297 nm and the run time 5min. Data were recorded and processed using TotalChromWS6.2 software package (Perkin Elmer, Spain). The analytical method was validated by determining analytical (linearity, detection limit, quantification limit, repeatability) and suitability (column efficiency, tailing factor) parameters according to the indications of ICH and USP.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Analytical results

Retention time of 5-ASA in all the dissolution media considered in this study was approximately 2.5 min. The detector response was linear in the range 5–100 μ g/ml in all the media (five data points, replicated three times, have been considered). Analytical and suitability parameters, calculated according to ICH and USP recommendations, are given in Table 1. The slope of the curve obtained by plotting the log of drug concentration vs the log of peak area (log-log slope) fulfilled ICH recommendations (0.95–1.05 accepted interval) in all the media, with a variation coefficient $\leq 1\%$. The limits of detection (LD) and quantification (LQ), determined from the signal-to-noise ratio, were < 1 μ g/ml. Repeatability (variation within-day) of peak area (A) and retention time (t_R), expressed as relative standard deviation (S_R), was always $\leq 1\%$. It was determined on the basis of nine analyses (three concentrations/three replicates each) of 5-ASA standard solutions covering the linearity range in all the media. Column efficiency, expressed as the number of theoretical plates (N), was about 8000 and tailing factor (T) was in the range 0.9–1.1, indicating that suitable peak symmetry was reached in all the media. Extraction recoveries were satisfactory and greater than 97% (ranging from 97.8% to 99.2%) for all samples tested.

3.2. Desorption isotherms

Desorption isotherms of 5-ASA-HL in water, pH 1.0 (0.1 M HCl) and pH 6.8 showed biphasic behaviour with turning points at approximately 0.2 h (10 min) (Fig. 1a), suggesting the contribution of more than one simple desorption process to the overall process of drug release. These results are in line with previous adsorption studies, where isotherms showed the contribution of two single processes in the global adsorption process; one on the external particle surface and/or inter-particle spaces and the other, probably occurring inside the HL tubes [28,31].

Adsorption of adsorbable solutes (A_{dis}) on solid sorbents (S_s) to give their corresponding solid adsorbates ($S-A_s$) [43-52] can be considered reversible adsorption-desorption phases as follows:

In the case of 5-ASA (adsorbable solute) and HL (solid sorbent), the overall adsorption process was the sum of two simple phases (rapid adsorption of 5-ASA on the external surface of individual HL particles or aggregates and slow adsorption of 5-ASA inside the pores of HL particles or aggregates) obeying to the following kinetic law [28]:

$$-\frac{dC}{dt} = k_a \cdot C^n \cdot (1 - \theta) - k_d \cdot \theta \quad (2)$$

where C is the drug concentration in solution, k_a the specific adsorption rate, k_d the specific desorption rate, n is the partial reaction order in C , and θ the fraction of surface active sites in the sorbent occupied by the sorbate, given by:

$$\theta = \frac{n^s}{n_m^s} = \frac{C_0 - C}{C_0 - C_e}$$

where n^s is the number of active sites occupied in the sorbent, n_m^s the total number of active sites of the sorbent, C_0 the initial drug concentration, and C_e the drug concentration at the equilibrium.

Release of 5-ASA from 5-ASA-HL can be considered the phase of desorption of the previously adsorbed drug molecules. In this solid/liquid interface process will be involved different simple interface processes leading to the transport of the drug from the solid (5-ASA-HL) to the liquid phase (surrounding medium). These simple processes may be governed by diffusion and in our particular case include: desorption of the drug adsorbed on the external HL surface and/or interparticle spaces (weakly influenced by diffusion across solid/liquid interface) and desorption of drug molecules adsorbed into HL pores and tubes. Independently of the influence of diffusion, both processes are interface processes and the kinetic law governing the overall release process can be expressed as the inverse of that described for adsorption:

$$\frac{dC}{dt} = -k_a \cdot C \cdot (1 - \theta) + k_d \cdot \theta \quad (3)$$

where the fraction of active sites in the sorbent occupied is given by:

$$\theta = \frac{n^s}{n_m^s} = \frac{C_e - C}{C_e}$$

Eq. (3) corresponds to reversible first order processes ($n = 1$) with respect to the concentration of drug in the dissolution medium. Integration of Eq. (3) yields:

$$C_t = C_e \left[1 - \exp\left(\frac{-k_d t}{C_e}\right) \right] \quad (4)$$

where C_t is the drug concentration in solution at time t , C_e is the drug concentration in solution at the equilibrium and k_d the specific desorption (release) rate.

Eq. (4) can be expressed as a function of the fraction of drug released (F) at time t :

$$F = \frac{C_t}{C_e} = 1 - \exp\left(\frac{-k_d \cdot t}{C_e}\right) \quad (5)$$

Eq. (5) can be modified depending on the number of simple processes involved in drug release. In the case

of 5-ASA-HL, two simple desorption phases (1 and 2) were expected to contribute to the overall release process; rapid desorption from the external clay mineral surface and slow diffusion of drug molecules from the interior of the halloysite tubes. In this case, Eq. (5) becomes:

$$F = \frac{C_{e(1)}}{C_{\infty}} \left[1 - \exp \left(\frac{-k_{d(1)} \cdot t}{C_{e(1)}} \right) \right] + \frac{C_{e(2)}}{C_{\infty}} \left[1 - \exp \left(\frac{-k_{d(2)} \cdot t}{C_{e(2)}} \right) \right] \quad (6)$$

where $C_{e(1)}$ and $k_{d(1)}$ are drug concentration at the equilibrium and specific desorption rate for process 1; $C_{e(2)}$ and $k_{d(2)}$ are drug concentration at the equilibrium and specific desorption rate for process 2; $C_{\infty} = C_{e(1)} + C_{e(2)}$.

Experimental results shown in Fig. 1a were fitted both to Eq. (5), considering only one release process, and Eq. (6) for two simultaneous release phases. In the first case (Eq. (5)), fitting was not considered satisfactory ($R^2 \cong 0.83$), whereas good correlations ($R^2 \geq 0.998$) were found using Eq. (6) in the three media (Table 2). Comparison between water and hydrochloric acid shows that release parameters (specific desorption rates ($k_{d(1)}$, $k_{d(2)}$) and $C_{e(1)}$) were greater in acidic medium (Table 2). This was not initially expected taking into account that the drug, weakly acid (pK_a , 25 °C: 3.0 (-COOH), 6.0 (-NH³⁺), 13.9 (-OH)), should be less dissociated (consequently less soluble) in acid than in water. However, the introduction of an electrolyte (chloride, strong acid) increased the ionic strength of the medium, increasing the solubility of 5-ASA (weak electrolyte). Release profile (Fig. 1a) and kinetic parameters (Table 2) obtained in pH 6.8 were very similar to pH 1.0, being also in this case higher than in water. This observation supports the hypothesis that the observed greater release in acid and buffer respect to water was probably due to the effect of ionic strength. Fig. 1b–d shows theoretical overall release curves (solid lines) calculated according to Eq. (6) and contribution of simple release processes (dotted lines) for each of the studied medium. Fast process (blue line) was assigned to desorption of 5-ASA molecules adsorbed on the outer surface of HL particles, being practically completed at about 0.2 h and having very high specific desorption rate ($k_{d(1)} \approx 2000 \text{ h}^{-1}$) (Table 2). This suggested a strong affinity of the drug for the surrounding media, causing that release of drug molecules adsorbed to the outer surface of the adsorbent was very easy and quickly. Red lines define slow desorption processes ($k_{d(2)} \approx 9\text{--}13 \text{ h}^{-1}$), consisting in diffusion (governed by concentration gradient) of drug molecules from inside the HL tubes to the solid/liquid interface. It can be considered that after rapid process was concluded ($\approx 0.2\text{h}$), drug release from 5-ASA-HL was due solely to a diffusive contribution. The sum of the two mentioned simple desorption processes (fast and slow) defined the overall release curves (solid lines) that described satisfactorily ($R^2 = 0.9980\text{--}0.9999$) the experimental results in the three media. (For interpretation of the references to color in the text, the reader is referred to the web version of this article). Release profile obtained by changing pH of the medium showed a very sharp turning point at 2 h (Fig. 2a). In order to establish if this result was effectively due to the pH or to the dilution of the medium (produced by adding 175 ml of tribasic sodium phosphate solution to the initial volume of hydrochloridric acid), desorption study was also performed on water only (525 ml in the early stage (0-2 h); 700 ml for $t \geq 2$ h). Results confirmed that the observed behaviour was due to the dilution of the medium in contact with the dispersed adsorbate, being the release profile in water very similar to that obtained when pH was changed (Fig. 2a, detail). Fig. 2a also showed a turning point in the early stage of the curve (approximately 0.2 h). This suggested that again more than one simple phase of desorption was involved in release process. In order to highlight all possible processes implicated in drug release, analysis of the experimental curve was done considering acid (0-2 h) and buffer (2-8 h) stage separately. The first section (0-2h; acid stage) corresponded to the sum of two simple simultaneous processes, being adequately ($R^2 = 0.9977$) described by Eq. (6) (Table 2). Value of $k_{d(1)}$ was similar to that observed in the case of 0.1 M HCl, which is not surprising, bearing in mind that this process was very fast and completed at very low time (less than a 0.2 h). In contrast, the value of $k_{d(2)}$ was somewhat lower than that calculated previously (0.1 M HCl). This is in line with the lower volume of medium (525 ml vs 700 ml) used in this case. For the same reason, $C_{e(1)}$ and $C_{e(2)}$ were lower compared to those found for pH 1.0 (Table 2). In the final section of the curve ($t \geq 2$ h), it was considered that only the “slow simple process in basic medium” (Fig. 2b; green line) was involved in drug release, since the so-called “fast simple process” (Fig. 2b; red line) and the “slow simple process in

acid medium" (Fig. 2b; blue line) were completed. Accordingly, in this case, Eq. (5) was able to satisfactorily ($R^2 = 0.9981$) describe experimental data (Table 2), whereas Eq. (6) did not provide good correlation ($R^2 = 0.8632$). The calculated specific desorption rate (k_d) was higher than that observed in the previous (acid) stage for the same process ($k_{d(2)}$) (Table 2). This could be explained considering that in buffer stage a dilution effect was produced (by addition of phosphate solution), increasing concentration gradient and therefore accelerating drug diffusion. (For interpretation of the references to color in the text, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Calculated correlation coefficients (Table 2) suggested that the proposed equations could be considered sufficiently adequate to describe release kinetic of 5-ASA from 5-ASA-HL in all the media considered in this study. Nevertheless, to confirm the suitability of the hypothesis, experimental data were also fitted to other models, widely used in literature. Calculated R^2_{adjusted} (Table 3) were sufficiently explicit to suggest that the equations proposed in this paper provided better correlation with experimental results, whereas equations of Higuchi, first order, Weibull and cube root models were not useful in studying release kinetic from 5-ASA-HL adsorbate ($R^2_{\text{adjusted}} \leq 0.9758$). "Power law" equation showed very good correlation coefficients ($R^2_{\text{adjusted}} > 0.999$). However, it should be remarked that these values did not include all the data, since this equation cannot be applied for amount of drug released $>60\%$ [27]. Application of "Power law" equation to the overall data would result in correlation coefficients <0.98 .

On the basis of the discussed results, it can be concluded that, in the case studied, the postulated kinetic model is the more convenient to describe the behaviour of the studied system. Moreover, the proposed model satisfies the physicochemical constraints requested to any model pretended to describe a physicochemical process.

4. Conclusions

Any postulated model to describe a process must fully justify it, in this case fit all experimental results. Among the different models tested in this paper, only the model assuming that two reversible and simultaneous adsorption-desorption processes were involved in the release process lead to satisfactory fitting of experimental curves. Consequently, it possible to postulate that desorption of 5- ASA from HL tubes can be described as the sum of two first order processes, one of which (slower) strongly controlled by diffusion of drug molecules (from interior of HL tubes to the solid-liquid interface). Accordingly, release rate enhanced with increasing the concentration gradient that controls the diffusive process. Ionic strength also produced higher release rates, while the influence of the pH seemed to be insignificant. Finally, although equations such as the "power law" were able to adequately describe the first part (up to 60%) of the release curve, the equations proposed in this paper were not limited by the experimental points to be considered, providing satisfactory fitting of all experimental data.

Equations based on kinetic laws describing reversible adsorption-desorption processes between drug molecules and solid carriers have been satisfactorily used to characterise *in vitro* drug release profiles from an inorganic solid adsorbent, providing information about kinetic order and specific release rate.

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TABLES

Table 1. Analytical and suitability parameters of HPLC method.

Medium	Linearity (log-log slope)	Repeatability (S_R %)		Efficiency (N)	T	Recovery (%)
		A	t_R			
Purified water	1 (0.007)	2.19	0.08	8142	1.1	97.8 (0.15)
0.1 M HCl (pH 1.0)	0.96 (0.003)	0.22	0.08	8537	0.91	98.3 (0.08)
pH 6.8	0.98 (0.007)	0.82	0.08	8275	0.86	99.2 (0.11)

Values in parentheses are variation coefficients (%)

Table 2. Values of kinetic parameters obtained from the proposed equations.

Medium	Eq. (5)	Eq. (6)			R^2			
		C_e (%)	k_d (h^{-1})	$C_{e(1)}$ (%)				
Purified water		-	-	60.2	1929	39.8	8.79	0.9980
0.1 M HCl (pH 1.0)		-	-	70.3	2345	29.6	9.18	0.9999
pH 6.8		-	-	68.2	2024	31.8	12.79	0.9998
Sequential pH	Acid stage (pH 1.0)	-	-	61.8	2265	17.6	6.76	0.9977
	Buffer stage (pH 6.8)	17.6	9.03	-	-	-	-	0.9981

Table 3. Correlation coefficients obtained fitting experimental results to the proposed equations and the other models considered in this study.

Model	$R^2_{adjusted}$		
	Purified water	pH 1.0	pH 6.8
Proposed equations	0.9978	0.9997	0.9996
Higuchi or "square root"	0.8652/0.9577 ^a	0.8523/0.9498 ^a	0.8678/0.9584 ^a
Peppas or "power law"	0.9777/0.9993 ^a	0.9674/0.9990 ^a	0.9699/0.9994 ^a
First order	0.8247	0.8321	0.8287
Weibull	0.9608	0.9758	0.9603
Hixson and Crowell or "cube root"	0.8106	0.8022	0.8169

^a Values obtained considering only drug released <60%.

FIGURES

Fig. 1. Amount of drug released (mean values \pm s.d.; n = 6) from 5-ASA-HL in the three media considered (a) and theoretical dissolution curves (lines) of overall and simple release processes in purified water (b), 0.1 M HCl (c) and pH 6.8 buffer (d).

Fig. 2. Amount of drug released (mean values \pm s.d.; n = 6) from 5-ASA-HL in sequential pH (the arrow indicates the time at which the pH of the medium was changed) and water (detail) (a) and theoretical dissolution curves (b).